

DEVELOPING PRINCIPLE OF MEASURING FLUIDS LINEAR AND VOLUMETRIC VELOCITY IN HORIZONTAL WELLS

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Abstract

Potential global growing energy demand to be a realistic script for the coming decades. Sources have emerged as an alternative, oil has continued to be the most important source of energy so far (32.9% of the total; World Energy Council, 2016) and may remain the main option in the long term. Recent major oil discoveries are in offshore fields where oil production is still difficult. Although new technologies have been developed, the lack of a clear understanding of the multiphase flow has imposed restrictions on projecting the directional wells.

Keywords: multiphase flow, flow velocity, horizontal well, updraft, downdraft

One of the actual tasks of modern field geophysics in operating horizontal wells is the determination of phase flow rates with an assessment of the interval production rate. Currently, mechanical flowmeters are traditionally used to measure the flow rate in the well. Unfortunately, the method has significant limitations, especially in multiphase flow conditions. A mechanical turbine is critical to the fluid composition, and phase separation in an inclined or horizontal well adds uncertainty due to its uncontrolled position relative to the interface [1].

Issue partially resolved through the use of distributed mechanical flowmeters that provide layer measurement of the local flow velocity in operating horizontal wells in combination with composition sensors [2]. However, under the conditions of water intrusion and low flow rates, it's typical for horizontal wells in most fields in Russian Federation.

The technology of operating inclined-directional and horizontal wells is widely used in every oil field in this country and abroad, along with constantly improving technology for drilling inclined-directional wells and well completions [1-3]. Compared to a vertical well, the underground environment of a highly deviated well and a horizontal well is undervalued [4-5]. Basically the following facts were shown:

1) the well gravity direction is perpendicular to the well axis direction, and the space around the well is asymmetric.

2) Stratified flow is common in multi-phase flow for gravity differentiation, and the flow modes are very complex due to the change in angle of the wellbore inclination.

3) There are three types due to wavy wellbore, including horizontal flow (inclination angle $(\alpha=0^0)$, updraft $(\alpha > 0^0)$, and liquid flows upwards), and downdraft $(\alpha < 0^0)$, liquid flows downwards). Thus, the traditional

multiphase flow interpretation model in a vertical well can't be effectively used to interpret well GIS data in highly inclined-directional and horizontal wells.

In this article, based on the theory of similarity, using a combination of instruments for production logging from SONDEX, experiments were carried out in a plexiglass pipe to simulate two-phase oil-water and gas-water phases in updraft, horizontal and downdraft flow, with an inner diameter of 124 mm. Based on the analysis conclusions of experimental data and considering such factors of influence, as the angle of inclination, models for correcting the well curves for the slippage velocity in inclined-directional and horizontal wells are created and preliminary verified.

Qualitative Analysis is estimated for the flow characteristics of two-phase oil-water and gas-water systems, so this article uses the example of two-phase oil-water system to analyze the slippage velocity of flow characteristics at different inclination angles [6-8]. Figure 1 shows a diagram of oil-water two-phase flow distributions and velocity profile in a wave-like well. Assuming that the fluid flow is from right to left;

1) updraft ($c > b$), accumulation of oil in the upper part of the pipe, and the buoyancy component of the oil takes away the bottom water with updraft, as well as the velocity of oil more than water. When moving into position, the buoyancy component of oil is equal to or less than the gravitational component of water, the water stops or sinks down, thereby forming a circulating water flow (or regurgitation), the oil velocity is positive, the water velocity is close to 0 or has a negative value.

2) When the wellbore is located horizontally, oil is at the top, water is at the bottom, and the difference in the rates of oil and water is low.

3) Downdraft ($b > a$), since the density of water is higher than that of oil, the velocity of downward water is higher than that of oil.

Figure 1– Oil and water distribution

Figure 2– Values depending on the water flow velocity

In a vertical well, the traditional calculation formula for the slippage velocity in a two-phase oil-water mixture is:

$$V_{SV} = 12.013 (p_W - p_o)^{0.25} \exp \left\{ -0.788 \ln \left[\frac{1.85}{p_W - p_o} \right] \times (1 - Y_W) \right\}, (1)$$

In a highly inclined well, the slippage rate is affected by differences in the density of each phase and the gravity component. In other words, the larger the angle of inclination, the more obvious the effect of gravity, so the sliding velocity can be corrected using the angle of inclination.

$$V_s = V_{SV} + V_{SC} = V_{SV} + f(\theta)$$

$$V_s = 12.013 (p_W - p_o)^{0.25} \exp \left\{ -0.788 \ln \left[\frac{1.85}{p_W - p_o} \right] \times (1 - Y_W) \right\} (1 + \lambda \theta), (2)$$

Where SV and SC are the corrected slippage velocity and correction value, m/min.

$f(\theta)$ is the correction of inclination angle,
 θ is inclination correction factor,
 Y_W is zero dimensions of water,
 $p_W - p_o$ are densities of water and oil,

Conclusion

1. There is still a slippage velocity between two-phase oil-water and gas-water mixtures in a highly inclined and horizontal well. The slippage velocity is strongly influenced by the well trajectory. In updraft, the slippage velocity is often positive. In horizontal flow, the sliding velocity is over 0, but close 0. In downdraft, the slippage velocity is negative.

2. Based on the analysis of the flow characteristics in the simulated experiments and theoretical multiphase flow models, with the introduction of the concept of well deviation correction, models are determined for adding and multiplying the well deviation correction by the slippage velocity. And the multiplier correction model has been proven correct and feasible in highly inclined and horizontal wells by verification two-phase oil-water experimental data.

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**RESEARCH OF THE RANDOM PROCESS LOAD CURRENT OF THE TRANSFORMER
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**ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ ВИПАДКОВОГО ПРОЦЕСУ СТРУМУ НАВАНТАЖЕННЯ
ТРАНСФОРМАТОРНОЇ ПІДСТАНЦІЇ**

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Abstract

In article the technique of the analysis of electrical loads of consumers as non-stationary casual processes with hidden periodicities is submitted. The estimation of outcomes of decomposition of casual process in a trigonometrical series happens on the basis of inspection of statistical hypotheses. The obtained performances of investigated casual process can be used for prediction of his extremes, and also for the purposes of optimum control.

Анотація

В статті представлена методика аналізу електричних навантажень потребителів як нестационарних випадкових процесів з прихованими періодичностями. Оцінювання результатів розкладання випадкового